

DESIGNING AN OUTCOMES – BASED SYLLABUS IN ENGINEERING ETHICS

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Abstract: With the impending Commission on Higher Education (CHED) memorandum order on the implementation of an outcomes-based education in engineering and technology, higher education institutions should start the groundwork for its full implementation. Preparations should include drafting of program educational objectives and student or program outcomes and design and creation of a continuous quality implement system. Curriculum mapping, syllabus designing, and identification of assessment and evaluation processes should follow. As stated above, the student or program outcomes form part of an outcomes-based education for international accreditation. One of these outcomes states that “Engineering programs must demonstrate that their graduates have an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility.” Thus, in this paper, the authors will present an outcomes-based syllabus for the prescribed course in ethics in all Philippine engineering curricula. This is the primary course where the attainment of such program / student outcome could be assessed and evaluated, although such outcome could also be assessed and evaluated in other courses such as methods of research, environmental engineering, engineering design and safety engineering.

Keywords: Outcomes-based education, program educational objectives, program/student outcomes, engineering ethics

1. Introduction

Ethics has become more increasingly important both in the academe and industry, in teaching and research and in the practice of the profession. Dr. Michael Davis, professor of engineering ethics at the Illinois Institute of Technology in Chicago, Illinois and seminar-workshop facilitator at the Institute’s Ethics Across the Curriculum program argues that there exists an ethics boom today which he describes as an increased awareness and heightened interest in the study of ethics. He enumerates the evidence of such a boom such as the increase in the number of publications in ethics, codes of ethics, seminars, courses and trainings and academic centers for the study of ethics. In a survey done by the American Society of Mechanical Engineers in the 1990s to academe and industry on what emerging engineers should know, the respondents ranked high the importance of professional ethics for new graduates in mechanical engineering with the industry’s rank higher than the academia. With these developments, it is therefore imperative for the academia to promote the importance of ethics education to their students especially in engineering realizing the

growing number of ethical issues and concerns, both simple and complex ones, related to their jobs as future engineers.

2. Engineering Ethics and Engineering Curriculum

There are many ways of teaching and integrating ethics in the curriculum. A course in ethics could be a stand-alone or independent course, a required or an elective course or topics in ethics could be integrated in an existing course or across the curriculum. Whichever way it may be, it is extremely important to communicate to both the students and faculty that ethics in engineering is not peripheral but an integral part of engineering education. In that case, it may be advantageous to adopt the ethics across the curriculum scheme wherein topics in ethics are integrated in as many courses as possible such as in lecture and design courses. Students will not only see the direct application of ethical principles, theories or codes in engineering, but will also be inculcated with the value of such concerns. In the Philippine engineering curricula prescribed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), topics in ethics are integrated in a required course (Engineering Law, Ethics and Contracts) wherein the number of credit units of such varies from one engineering discipline to another. Furthermore, the CHED memorandum order on the undergraduate mechanical engineering program in 2008 specifies a program outcome that states that students should develop the ability to understand their ethical responsibility [1]. With this particular program outcome, it is necessary to develop an outcomes-based course syllabus which will help in the attainment of the outcome not only in one particular course, but also in several courses as well. However, the number of courses that focus on the mentioned outcome must be limited to make sure that a thorough and accurate assessment and evaluation of the attainment of the ethics outcome is done.

3. Engineering Ethics Course Syllabus

A syllabus is a map of Learning Activities (LAs) and assessment methods that serves as a guide for both the students and faculty in order to achieve the course Learning Outcomes (LOs). Thus, it is important that the syllabus is well – crafted considering that it sends a message to the students that the instructor is organized, cares about the student learning and will create an effective learning experience [2]. In designing a syllabus, it is helpful to remember that what the students do is actually more important in determining what is learned than what the teacher does [3]. The engineering ethics syllabus that the authors designed follows an outcomes-based format which contains the following components: course title and description, course learning objectives and outcomes, course learning plan, course assessment, references and class policies.

The course description gives the summary of what the course is all about. The description indicates what the nature of the course is (whether foundational, core, major or integrative), the topics to be covered, the specific approaches and the general aims. It also includes the requisite courses needed in order for the students to qualify to enrol in this course. For the engineering ethics syllabus, the course description was lifted from the CHED CMO No.9 Series of 2008 – Policies and Guidelines for the degree Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering (BSME). The course title is ME Laws, Ethics, Codes and Standards and deals with the study of the mechanical engineering law, code of ethics, ethical theories, and ethical issues in the practice of engineering. It also familiarizes the students with the technical codes and standards used by mechanical engineers.

Student or program outcomes are statements that describe the expectations from the students upon graduation in terms of what they should know and what they could do [4]. These relate to the skills, knowledge, behaviour and values that students acquire as they progress through the program. For the BSME program, the CHED identified 9 program outcomes and one of this is that the graduate of BSME program must have attained the ability to understand professional and ethical responsibility. This particular student outcome can be addressed in the course Engineering Ethics. As can be seen from appendix 1, topics covered in this course include ME Code of Ethics, ethical theories and ethical issues and case studies in engineering. On the other hand, course LOs are statements that tell us what the students should be able to know and do if they were able to acquire the knowledge and skills that they are supposed to learn from the course. These statements should be specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and time – bound. Make sure that the LOs are clearly stated and aligned with the student outcomes.

For the course Engineering Ethics, three LOs were formulated which are aligned with the program outcomes. These LOs are the following: A student completing the course should at the minimum be able to:

1. Resolve hypothetical moral dilemmas in the mechanical engineering profession with the use of ethical theories and concepts, and ethical problem solving techniques.
2. Remember important and critical provisions of the mechanical engineering law.
3. Remember the concepts and the nature of contracts.

After the LOs are formulated, one should select the teaching methods or LAs that will be utilized to conduct the class. These activities must be aligned with the LOs for the course. Referring to Appendix 1, the following LAs will be utilized for the delivery of the topics in the course: lecture, oral reports, class discussion, debate, mini ethics bowl and role playing (with video). Through these various LAs, the students will be able to understand the concepts of engineering ethics, apply these to the various case studies that will be discussed in class and thoroughly develop a sense of professional and ethical responsibility.

The assessment methods for the course will then be determined and these should be aligned with the LOs. These should evaluate student progress and should serve as a measure if the desired LOs were achieved. In this course the following will be used to assess the student's performance: midterm and final exams, mini – ethics bowl, term project, and class participation. An example grading system and rubric for the mini – ethics bowl is found in Appendix 1. This rubric will tell the students how their works will be graded by their professors. The grading system in terms of percentage for every requirement is also included in the syllabus.

The list of references is also included in the syllabus. As much as possible, these reference materials should be copyrighted within the last five years.

Another important aspect of an outcomes – based syllabus is that it should include the class policies which may be derived from the student handbooks and other sources. These policies will make it easy for the students to know what to do, for example, in case that he was not able to take the midterm or final exam due to uncontrolled circumstances.

4. Assessment and Evaluation of the Program Outcome

This section discusses the assessment and evaluation methods, which can be utilized for the course.

4.1 Assessment of Program Outcomes

It is important to note that different assessments of performance are done within a course. Student performance for a course, based on several factors (e.g. quantitative test items, grammar and proper effective composition for essays, project quality and content, etc.), tends to be represented by a standard grade point at the end of the course. The grade point of the student is usually a converted numerical value, taken from the student's final grade- a summation which is computed from scores from different class activities of varying weights. Due to the many and high variability of inputs that make up the final grade, it is strongly advised not to use aggregated scores to represent the degree of attainment of student outcomes.

Assessment tools should be planned and chosen properly in order to reflect the student's attainment of the outcome. A tool or a set of tools must be developed to make sure that educators accurately gather data that could be used to determine the extent to which the outcomes have been attained. These tools may be in the form of LAs that are utilized for the course.

For the syllabus developed by the authors, three assessment tools were assigned to measure outcomes attainment, each tool to be utilized for each LO. One relevant LA was also selected to assess each of the LOs for the course. These selected LAs include the mini-ethics bowl and relevant portions of both the midterm and final examinations, representing the three LOs identified.

The assessment tools should be able to measure the LO attainment. An example of this would be to create an assessment system to measure the degree to which a student can resolve a moral dilemma during the mini-ethics bowl using techniques and concepts discussed in class. The result of the assessment could be numerical or alphabetical, and may also be used for student performance scoring for the final grade. The data resulting from the assessment must not be aggregated, taking note of the attainment scores obtained by each student for each LO. The data collected may now be used for evaluation of the degree of attainment of the program outcome.

4.2 Evaluation of Program Outcomes

After the data from the assessment process have been obtained, the instructor would need to interpret the relevance and meaning of the data. The consolidated data would then reflect the number of students in the course who have exhibited the degree of attainment for each LO. The criteria for the evaluation should be decided upon by the concerned personnel of the Higher Education Institution (e.g. the department or college offering the course) at the beginning of the assessment cycle.

As an example, for an assessment system using a rubric of one (very poor) to five (excellent) the Institution may determine that 90 percent of the students in the course should have earned scores of at least four (good). The distribution of the students' attainment of the outcomes becomes the basis for the instructor to evaluate the degree of how the LOs have been satisfied. The results of the evaluation could then translate into the level of attainment of the program outcome for the particular course, which in turn will be part of the collection of data resulting from various courses.

As part of the continuous quality improvement process, the information obtained from evaluation could be used by the instructors to identify areas of improvement that could be focused on to further benefit the students and to ensure the realization of the attainment of the program outcomes.

5. Conclusion

Various factors have driven the push towards implementing outcomes-based education in the Philippines, which include global trends on education, various literature on outcomes-based teaching and learning and the CHED's initiatives. In combination with the global need for much more effective teaching and learning models for engineering ethics, the curriculum and syllabi of courses that provide opportunity for the students' development of ethical autonomy should be reconsidered. Outcomes-based education provides the structure for engineering schools to realistically evaluate the level at which expected outcomes have been attained by their respective programs.

One of the critical points for an effective outcomes-based ethics course would be the development of an effective syllabus, which reflects specifically what outcomes are expected to be attained by students by the end of the course and program. The development of such a syllabus would also help instructors focus more on LAs and LOs that are more relevant and effective in terms of the attainment of the program outcomes. The paper provides a guide for concerned engineering programs in their own efforts of continually striving towards improved teaching and learning of engineering ethics. In the end, the beneficiaries of such push towards an effective outcomes-based education, particularly in engineering ethics, will be the students, the various educational institutions, the different professions and the nation.

References

- [1] CHED, *CHED memorandum order No. 09 series 2008*, Pasig City, Philippines, (2008).
- [2] University of West Florida, Center for University Teaching, Learning and Assessment (uwf.edu/cutla/frs-syllabus.cfm)
- [3] *Aligning Teaching and Assessing to Course Objectives*, John Biggs, 2003.
- [4] ABET, *Criteria for Accrediting Engineering Programs*, ABET, Inc., Baltimore, MD, (2008).
- [5] School of Mechanical Engineering, *Course syllabus in Contracts, Specification, Mechanical Engineering Law and Ethics*, Mapua Institute of Technology, Intramuros, Manila, (2012).
- [6] Department of Mechanical Engineering, *Course Syllabus in Engineering Law, Ethics and Contracts*, De La Salle University-Manila, (2012).

Appendix 1- Course Syllabus [5] [6]

Course Title: ME Laws, Ethics, Codes and Standards

Credit Units: 3 units

Pre – requisites: None

Course description: The course deals with the study of the Mechanical Engineering law, code of ethics, ethical theories, and ethical issues in the practice of engineering. Familiarization with the technical codes and standards are included.

Program Outcomes	Learning Outcomes
An ability to understand professional and ethical responsibility	<p>A student completing the course should at the minimum be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resolve hypothetical moral dilemmas in the mechanical engineering profession with the use of ethical theories and concepts, and ethical problem solving techniques. 2. Remember important and critical provisions of the Mechanical Engineering Law. 3. Remember the concepts and the nature of contracts.

Learning Plan

Learning Outcome	Topic	Week No.	Learning Activities
LO2	The Mechanical Engineering Profession	1	Lecture, Class Discussion
LO2	The Mechanical Engineer in Society	2	Lecture, Class Discussion
LO2	The Mechanical Engineering Law	3	Oral Report, Class Discussion
LO1, LO2	The Mechanical Engineer's Code of Ethics	4, 5	Lecture, Class Discussion
LO1	Ethical Theories (Duty Ethics, Right Ethics, Utilitarianism and Virtue Ethics)	6, 7	Case Studies, Debate, Class Discussion
	Midterm Exam	7	

Learning Outcome	Topic	Week No.	Learning Activities
LO1, LO2	Ethical Issues and Case Studies in Engineering	8, 9, 10	Case Studies, Mini – Ethics Bowl, Role Playing (Video)
LO1, LO3	Local and International Codes and Standards	10, 11	Oral Report, Class Discussion
LO1, LO3	Contracts and specifications	12, 13	Lecture, Case Studies, Class Discussion
Final Exam		14	

Sample Grading System (Mini Ethics Bowl)

Criteria for Assessment	Description	Weight of Scores for Class Grading	Learning Outcome Assessment
Clarity and Intelligibility	Student was able to present position in a logical and consistent manner	25	(see rubric)
Depth and Substance	Student was able to identify and discuss the ethical factors relevant to the case	25	(see rubric)
Ethical Relevance	Student was able to present position without inclusion of factors that are irrelevant/have minor relevance	25	(see rubric)
Deliberative Thoughtfulness	Student was able to consider various different viewpoints and alternatives, considering perception of other stakeholders	25	(see rubric)

Sample Rubric for Mini Ethics Bowl (Second Criteria: Depth and Substance)

Assessment Score	Description	Details
1	Very Poor	Student failed to identify/discuss any ethical factors or considerations that are relevant to the given case.
2	Poor	Student was able to identify and discuss some relevant ethical factors/ considerations, but such were considerably minor and insufficient to support argument.
3	Fair	Student was able to identify and discuss some relevant ethical factors/ considerations enough to support argument, but lacks depth of analysis of factors in relation to the case
4	Good	Student was able to identify and discuss the relevant ethical factors/ considerations and provided a sound analysis to relate the identified factor(s) to the case.
5	Excellent	Student was able to identify and discuss critical and important relevant ethical factors/ considerations, providing both a clear link and an in-depth analysis that strongly relates the identified factor(s) to the case.

Grading System

The student will be graded according to the following:

Midterm Exam	-	20%
Final Exam	-	30%
Mini – Ethics Bowl	-	20%
Term Project (Video)	-	20%
Class Participation	-	10%

Total	-	100%

Passing: 60%

References:

1. Engineering Ethics: Concepts and Cases by Harris, Pritchard and Rabins, 2009
2. Engineering Ethics, 3rd edition, by Charles Fledderman, 2008
3. Introduction to Engineering Ethics by Schinzinger and Martin, 2000
4. Ethical Issues in Engineering by Deborah Johnson, 1991
5. Contracts, Specifications and Engineering Relations by Mead, Mead and Akeman
6. Philippine Society of Mechanical Engineers Code
7. Philippine Mechanical Engineering Law

Class Policies

1. There will be a midterm and a final exam in this course. Make – up exams will be given provided the reason for not taking the exam is excused as stipulated in the student handbook.
2. Regular attendance is expected. Attendance policy as stipulated in the student handbook will be implemented.
3. Students are encouraged to see the faculty during the scheduled consultation periods in case they have questions regarding the topics discussed in class.